

Epiverse TRACE Pre-Summit Training Report

Outbreak Analytics and Applied Modelling with R

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Principal Investigators | Bubacarr Bah | Adam Kucharski | Zulma Cucunubál | Sebastian Funkl | Rosalind Eggo

Coordination | Alimatou Sallah | Gibril Gabbidon | Alannah Hog

Training Coordination | Abdoelnaser Degoot | Andree Valle-Campos | Laura Gómez-Bermeo

Support team | Karim Mané | Bankole Ahadzie | James Azam | Atta Lowe

Photographs | Mohammed Jobe

Editorial design of the report | David Gallo

Participants | **1.** Abdoulaye Sadio (M, Senegal) | **2.** Adanna Ezenwa-Ahanene (F, Nigeria) | **3.** Aji Fanna Boyé (F, Gambia) | **4.** Alhagie Papa Sey (M, Gambia) | **5.** Amadou Barry (M, Gambia) | **6.** Armando Sanyang (M, Gambia) | **7.** Azokpota Paustella (F, Benin) | **8.** Boris Tamegye (M, Cameroon) | **9.** Daniel Bekalo (M, Ethiopia) | **10.** Dawda Joof (M, Gambia) | **11.** Doris Nyamwaya (F, Kenya) | **12.** Ernest Bizimana (M, Rwanda) | **13.** Fatoumata Seck (F, Senegal) | **14.** Husain Drammeh (M, Gambia) | **15.** Irene Edward (F, Tanzania) | **16.** Joshua Atsu (M, Ghana) | **17.** Momodou Kalleh (M, Gambia) | **18.** Muhammed Bah (M, Gambia) | **19.** Muscline Ganda (F, Zimbabwe) | **20.** Kebba Jobarteh (M, Gambia) | **21.** Merveille Ndoba (F, D.R. Congo) | **22.** Sang Mendy (M, Gambia) | **23.** Shola Able-Thomas (M, Gambia) | **24.** Sokhna Bigué (F, Senegal) | **25.** Yankuba Fabureh (M, Gambia) | **26.** Ismaél Koné (M, Ivory Coast) | **27.** Mouhamadou F Diop (M, Senegal) | **28.** Solim PITIKALO (F, Togo) | **29.** Sani Amadou (M, Niger)

Overview

The Epiverse-TRACE initiative successfully conducted, for its first time in Africa, a training course on "Outbreak Analytics and Applied Modelling with R" at MRCG, Banjul, The Gambia from 25-29 December 2024. This training was facilitated by Epiverse-TRACE members from MRCG, LSHTM, and Pontificia Universidad Javeriana.

The course aimed to enhance participants' skills in outbreak analytics and applied modeling using R. A total of **151 applications** were received, with **29 participants** selected from **15 countries**, including The Gambia, Senegal, Niger, Ghana, Benin, Rwanda, Nigeria, Ivory Coast, Tanzania, Togo, Ethiopia, Zimbabwe, Kenya, DR Congo, and Cameroon. Women represented **35%** of the participants.

The training lasted **five days** (approximately **40 hours**) and focused on strengthening technical capabilities in outbreak analytics. The sessions were designed to provide both theoretical knowledge and practical hands-on experience in data analysis, modeling, and interpretation of epidemiological data. Participants engaged in interactive discussions, coding exercises, and real-world case studies to deepen their understanding of outbreak analytics.

Participant Demographics

- Over **60%** of participants work in the healthcare sector, including epidemiologists, public health officers, and researchers.
- The **average age** of participants was **32 years**, with a diverse mix of professionals from various backgrounds, including academia, governmental health agencies, and non-governmental organizations.
- Participants had varying levels of experience with R programming, from beginners to advanced users, allowing for peer-to-peer learning and collaboration.

Application and Selection Process

The course was widely advertised through multiple channels, including LSHTM webpage, the [summit webpage](#), and on social media outlets including [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#), and targeted mailing lists. The course did not have a registration fee and offered limited funding for travel and local expenses for international participants.

A total of **151 fully completed applications** were received. After a thorough review by selection committee, **30 applicants** were selected based on:

- **Professional background** in epidemiology, R programming, and data science
- **Geographical diversity** across African countries
- **Balanced gender representation**

The final cohort consisted of **15 local participants from The Gambia** and **15 from other African countries**. However, due to the absence of **three** international participants, additional local participants were invited to fill their spots, for which **two** of them were able to participate.

The figure below illustrates the distribution of participants with respect to nationality and gender.

Training Content

The training covered key topics, including:

- **Introduction to outbreak analytics** – Understanding key epidemiological concepts and their practical applications.
- **Refresher on R basics** – Setting up R and RStudio, basic syntax, and data manipulation.
- **Introduction to mathematical modeling of infectious diseases** – Exploring different modeling techniques and their use in predicting outbreak trends.
- **Simulating disease transmission with interventions** – Hands-on practice with scenario-based outbreak simulations.
- **Reading, cleaning, and standardizing outbreak case data** – Data preprocessing and quality control techniques.
- **Accessing epidemiological parameters** – Identifying key parameters such as reproduction numbers and attack rates.
- **Estimating transmission metrics** – Using statistical methods to evaluate outbreak dynamics.
- **Applied epidemiology R tutorials** – Step-by-step coding tutorials to reinforce learning.
- **Case study: Measles outbreak in Burkina Faso** – Analyzing a real-world outbreak scenario.
- **Introduction to SIR and SEIR models (video lesson)** – Understanding compartmental models and their applications in outbreak predictions.

Pre training materials

Pre-training materials were provided to support learning and ensure participants were prepared for the sessions. These materials included instructional videos, guided exercises, and reading resources covering the fundamentals of epidemiology and R programming.

Assessment

We assessed participants' understanding of the training topics through open-ended questions, hands-on exercises, outbreak data challenges, and interpretation of modeling results. [Mentimeter](#) was used as a real-time platform to collect participants' responses. Below are examples of such activities.

What order of tasks would you follow to use epidemiological distributions for R_t estimation?

What information can you provide to {EpiNow2} to estimate R_t ?

Satisfaction Levels for Different Aspects of Sessions

Furthermore, for all participants, the training met the proposed objectives, equipping them with relevant skills, practical knowledge, and confidence to apply outbreak analytics and modeling in their professional settings.

Satisfaction Levels for Different Aspects of Training

Focus Group Insights

As part of the focus group discussions, a Collaborative Opinion Mapping activity was conducted to visually collect participants' insights on the strengths and areas for improvement of the course. This exercise promoted reflection and facilitated group discussions on key aspects of the training. Participants contributed their thoughts using post-it notes on large posters categorized into four key areas:

- **Strengths of the Course:** Participants highlighted aspects they found most valuable, such as live coding exercises, case studies, and hands-on learning experiences.
- **Areas for Improvement:** Feedback included suggestions on topics that needed more depth, pacing adjustments, and clarity in certain sections.
- **Applicability to Professional Work:** Many participants shared how they plan to implement the acquired skills in their respective jobs and the challenges they might face.
- **Recommendations for the Future:** Suggestions included expanding training duration, integrating scenario modeling on vaccine effectiveness, and increasing interactive exercises.

This activity allowed participants to reflect individually before collaborating in teams, helping to identify common themes and areas for enhancement. The findings from this exercise reinforced the key strengths of the training while providing actionable insights for future improvements.

Participants highlighted several strengths of the training:

- **Clarity, relevance, and applicability** of the topics.
- **Live coding and case studies** enhanced understanding by providing real-world context.
- **Helpful packages and tools** provided practical, hands-on experience with data analysis.
- **Skilled and patient facilitators** ensured that no participant was left behind, fostering an inclusive learning environment.
- **Well-organized logistics and support team** contributed to a smooth and efficient training experience.
- **Pre-training materials** provided clear explanations and valuable context, helping participants familiarize themselves with key concepts before the sessions.

The following image provides a visual summary of the main topics and subtopics discussed during the focus group, highlighting the strengths of the course, areas for improvement, its applicability in professional settings, and recommendations for future editions

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Recommendations for Future Training

Participants suggested:

- **Increasing time** for studying transmissibility concepts and integrating more interactive exercises.
- **Enhancing participant interaction** during sessions through group projects and collaborative problem-solving.
- **Aligning the clarity between theoretical concepts and package applications** during live coding to strengthen comprehension.
- **Keeping the network of this cohort active** for ongoing collaboration and knowledge exchange.
- **Providing continuous capacity-building opportunities** such as webinars, follow-up training, and advanced courses.
- **Including scenario modeling on vaccine effectiveness** in future sessions to explore real-world policy implications.
- **Implementing project-based learning** by providing datasets for individual practice after the training, reinforcing skills learned during the sessions.
- **Creating internship programs** to encourage continuous learning and professional development.

Reflections from Participants

Some notable reflections from participants included:

- *"This training is important for my work as a surveillance officer, where data analysis is essential for informed decision-making."*
- *"I mainly work with Python, so discovering what R/Epiverse offers has been insightful. R appears less verbose than Python, which may speed up implementation."*
- *"The coding sessions improved my programming skills and my approach to problem-solving."*
- *"Applying these tools in real outbreak scenarios helps inform early decision-making and response strategies."*

Gratitude Board

As part of the closing activities, a Gratitude Board was introduced to allow participants to express their appreciation for different aspects of the training experience. This activity provided a space for participants to acknowledge and share their gratitude towards the facilitators, their peers, the organizing team, and their own personal growth during the course. Participants wrote messages on sticky notes, which were then placed on a collective board under different categories. These categories included:

- **To the Staff:** Appreciation for organizing and delivering the training.
- **To My Peers:** Acknowledgment of the support and collaboration among participants.
- **To Myself:** Personal reflections on growth and commitment to applying new skills.
- **To the Facilitators:** Recognition of the dedication, expertise, and support provided by the trainers.

This exercise fostered a sense of community and encouraged reflection on the impact of the training. It also reinforced the positive learning environment created throughout the sessions, highlighting the meaningful connections and experiences shared by participants.

- **To the Staff:** *"Thank you for thinking of Africa and supporting this training. We truly appreciated it."*
- **To My Peers:** *"I'm grateful to be part of this engaging and supportive community."*
- **To Myself:** *"I will challenge myself to spread this knowledge in my home country and public health institutions, ensuring more professionals benefit from these insights."*
- **To the Facilitators:** *"Congratulations! You did a great job. Thank you for your commitment and empathy. Your guidance made a significant impact."*

Conclusions

The training successfully enhanced the capacity of professionals in outbreak analytics and applied modeling using R. The strong engagement, positive feedback, and participant recommendations indicate a need for continued investment in such initiatives.

Future sessions can further strengthen the learning experience by increasing training duration, integrating project-based learning, and fostering a lasting network among participants. Additionally, expanding opportunities for hands-on practice and creating mentorship programs would enhance participants' ability to apply their skills in real-world outbreak response scenarios.

Ensuring that this cohort remains connected and engaged through follow-up initiatives will be key to sustaining the impact of the training. With continuous support, knowledge-sharing, and further skill development, this program can play a vital role in strengthening public health capacity across the region.